

An ordered pair approach to Fermat's last theorem under non- multiplicity of exponents.

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Abstract

If $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$ has ordered pair solution of coprime natural number (X,Y,Z) , (n is a prime number, and $n \nmid XYZ$)

This ordered pair (X,Y,Z) must satisfy the following three conditions:

① $(X,Y,Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$, where
 $\gcd(R,n)=1$, $\gcd(R,A)=1$, $\gcd(R,Z)=1$,
 $\gcd(A,Z)=1$, $\gcd(A,n)=1$

② $(X,Y,Z) = (LB, Z - L^n, Z)$, where
 $\gcd(L,n)=1$, $\gcd(L,A)=1$, $\gcd(L,Z)=1$,
 $\gcd(B,Z)=1$, $\gcd(B,n)=1$, $\gcd(R, L) = 1$

③ $X + Y = G^n, Z = GC$, where
 $\gcd(G, C) = 1$

Then if we combine ①,②,③,

$$\begin{aligned} X &= Z - R^n, Y = Z - L^n \\ X + Y &= 2Z - R^n - L^n = G^n \end{aligned}$$

$$Z = \frac{G^n + R^n + L^n}{2}$$

$$X = Z - R^n = \frac{G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}$$

$$Y = Z - L^n = \frac{G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}$$

Therefore we get coprime ordered pair (X, Y, Z) must satisfy the following form:

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n + L^n}{2} \right)$$

where G, R, L are coprime each other.

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$$(X, Y, Z) = \frac{1}{2}(G^n - R^n + L^n, G^n + R^n - L^n, G^n + R^n + L^n)$$

Chapter 0. Lemma

Chapter 0. Lemma

Lemma1. If there exists an ordered pair of natural numbers (X,Y,Z) , then there exists a coprime ordered pair of natural numbers (x,y,z) .

Infinite natural numbers with infinite 0s, such as $10000\dots$, are not treated as natural numbers. Why is that? Because the following question cannot be answered.

Is $10000\dots$ a multiple of 3?

If an infinite natural number like $10000\dots$ is divided by 3, the quotient is infinite. Since it is infinitely divisible, there is no such thing as a remainder. Therefore, there is no chance of a decimal point. Does that mean that $10000\dots$ is a multiple of 3? We may say yes.

However, it can be proven that 10^n , a power of 10, is not divisible by 3. This is because 10 and 3 are coprime, and no power of 10 can produce a factor of 3.

This is contradiction. It means that $10000\dots$ is not a normal natural number.

In fact, Fermat proved the case of $n = 4$ by the method of infinite descent. If there is an ordered pair of natural numbers satisfying the case of $n = 4$, then the ordered pair of natural numbers must be an infinitely small natural number, which was a contradiction.

So an ordered pair of natural numbers (x,y,z) has finite common divisor. So we can find a coprime ordered pair of natural numbers (x,y,z)

Lemma 2.

If $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$ has a coprime natural number ordered pair (x,y,z) , it is impossible for only two of the three numbers to have common divisors.

pf) If X and Y has common divisor A and Z is coprime to A,

$$X=Ax$$

$$Y=Ay$$

$$Z=Z$$

If you substitute it into the equation $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$,

$$A^n x^n + A^n Y^n = Z^n$$

$$A^n (x^n + y^n) = Z^n$$

$$x^n + y^n = \left(\frac{Z}{A}\right)^n$$

Since the left side is a natural number, the right side must also be a natural number.

But Z and A is coprime, which is contradiction.

The case where only Y and Z have a common divisor B can be proven in a similar way. (X,By,Bz)

$$X^n = B^n (z^n - y^n)$$

X and B is coprime. It is impossible.

Lemma 3. For r such that $0 < r < n$, nCr is a multiple of n . (n is a prime number, which is an index of Fermat equation)

pf) nCr is a natural number. In Pascal's triangle, we can inductively prove that these numbers are natural numbers.

$$nCr = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{(n-r)!r!}$$

But $(n-r)$, $(n-r-1)$, $(n-r-2)$, ... 2, 1 can't divide n because n is a prime number and $n-r < n$.

Similarly, r , $(r-1)$, $(r-2)$, $(r-3)$, ..., 2, 1 can't divide n so the denominator always has n . Thus, nCr is always a natural number that is a multiple of n .

Lemma4. The following equation is a contradiction:

$$p^2N = pK$$

where p is prime number, N is coprime to p , and K is coprime to p .

Because if you divide both sides by p , you get

$$pN = K$$

The left side is a multiple of p . But the right side is not a multiple of p .

This Lemma will play a very important role in the proof in chapters 2 and 3.

Lemma 5. $p \mid Y^n$ is equivalent to $p \mid Y$

(p is a prime number. And $p \mid Y^n$ means Y^n is a multiple of p .)

pf)

p is a prime number. so Y must have p as a prime factor. Let's assume that Y does not have p as a prime factor. Then p cannot be generated by raising Y to a power.

'Because p is a prime number.'

Chapter 1.

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, Y, Z)$$

(n is a prime number greater than or equal to 3)

Chapter 1.

$$\boxed{X^n + Y^n = Z^n}$$

Let's call it 'Fermat equation'.

(n is a prime number ($n \geq 3$), and X, Y, Z is coprime each other. By Lemma 1 and 2, we can choose coprime ordered pair (X, Y, Z))

Chapter 1-1

First, we will show that

$X=Z-p$ is impossible. p is any prime number and coprime to n .

That is, the difference between Z and X cannot be a prime number p .

pf)

$$\boxed{(X, Y, Z) = (Z - p, Y, Z) \text{ ----- } \text{---(A)}} \quad \text{---(A)}$$

Substitute this ordered pair into the Fermat equation.

$$(Z - p)^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

expand it.

$$\begin{aligned} Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-2} \\ + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-1} - p^n + Y^n = Z^n \end{aligned}$$

Note that n is a 'prime number' greater than or equal to 3. Since Z^n is common to both sides, subtract it and eliminate it.

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-2} \\
& + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-1} - p^n + Y^n = 0 \text{ ----- } \text{---}(\mathbb{B})
\end{aligned}$$

Let's move everything to the right side, leaving only Y^n on the left side.

$$\begin{aligned}
& Y^n \\
& = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p - \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^2 + \dots + \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-2} \\
& - \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-1} + p^n
\end{aligned}$$

By Lemma3, all terms on the right side have 'p' in common, they are grouped by p.

$$\begin{aligned}
& = p \left\{ \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} - \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p + \dots + \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-3} \right. \\
& \left. - \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-2} + p^{n-1} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$Y^n = p \times K$$

where K is a proper natural number.

Anyway, the right side is a multiple of p, so Y^n is a multiple of p.(by Lemma4.)

Since p is a prime number,

$$p \mid Y^n$$

means

$$p \mid Y$$

by Lemma5.

Since $p \mid Y$,

let $Y = py$ for a suitable natural number y .

and substitute it into (B)

$$\begin{aligned} & - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-2} \\ & + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-1} - p^n + (py)^n = 0 \end{aligned}$$

$\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p = nZ^{n-1} p$. Let's move this term to the right-hand side.

And divide both sides by p . Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-3} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-2} - p^{n-1} \\ & + p^{n-1} y^n = nZ^{n-1} \end{aligned}$$

Since all terms on the left-hand side have p as a factor, the left-hand side is a multiple of p .

$$\begin{aligned} & p \\ & \times \left\{ \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p^{n-4} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{n-3} - p^{n-2} \right. \\ & \left. + p^{n-2} y^n \right\} = nZ^{n-1} \end{aligned}$$

$$p \times N = nZ^{n-1}$$

N is a suitable natural number. Since left-hand side is a multiple of p , the right-hand side is also a multiple of p .

$$p \times N = nZ^{n-1}$$

Since p is a prime number, only two cases are possible.

i) $p \mid n$

ii) $p \mid Z^{n-1}$

Note that: ii) means $p \mid Z$. (\because Lemma 5.)

And ii) is impossible. Why?

$$(A) - \boxed{(X, Y, Z) = (Z - p, Y, Z)}$$

Since $p \mid Z$, let $Z = pz$ for the suitable natural number z .

Then $(X, Y, Z) = (pz - p, Y, pz)$

Look. $X = pz - p = p(z - 1) \rightarrow X$ is a multiple of p .

and Z is a multiple of p . (p is a prime number, so $p \geq 2$)

There is a common prime factor p between X and Z .

It is a contradiction by Lemma 2. If X and Z have a common prime factor p , then Y also has a common prime factor p by Lemma 2.

(X, Y, Z) have a common prime factor p .

We were looking for ordered pairs (X, Y, Z) that are coprime.

So this is a contradiction and case ii) is impossible.

How about case i)?

$p \mid n$. Since the exponent n is a prime number, $p=n$.

So substitute $p=n$ into (A) – $(X, Y, Z) = (Z - p, Y, Z)$

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - n, Y, Z)$$

Substitute this ordered pair into ‘Fermat equation’.

$$(Z - n)^n + Y^n = Z^n \text{ ----- (C)}$$

Expand it.

$$Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} n + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} n^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 n^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z n^{n-1} - n^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

Subtract Z^n from both sides to eliminate Z^n .

Let’s move all terms on the left-hand side except Y^n to the right-hand side.

$$Y^n = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} n - \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} n^2 + \dots + \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 n^{n-2} - \binom{n}{n-1} Z n^{n-1} + n^n$$

All terms on the right-hand side is a multiples of n .

So we can express the right-hand side as $n \times M$ for a proper natural number M .

$$Y^n = n \times M$$

Therefore, Y^n is a multiple of n .

$n \mid Y^n$ means $n \mid Y$.

Therefore it is impossible, because we are discussing the case where $n \nmid XYZ$.

Therefore, case i)- $p \mid n$
is also impossible.

In summary, if $X=Z-p$, only the following two cases were possible.

i) $p \mid n$

ii) $p \mid Z^{n-1}$

But we have so far shown that both of these cases are impossible.

Therefore, $X=Z-p$ is impossible.

There is never a case where X and Z differ by some arbitrary prime number p .

In chapter 1, I will continue to chain together this type of development. The end of this chain will be

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, Y, Z)$$

I will omit detailed explanations as long as the logic is similar to the previous proof(Chapter 1-1).

Chapter 1-2

$$X = Z - p_1 p_2 p_3 \cdots p_k$$

is impossible.

It means that the difference between Z and X cannot be the product of the first powers of prime numbers.

For example, Z=19, X=13 is impossible.

Because $Z - X = 6 = 2 \times 3$

If we express this as an ordered pair,

$$\boxed{(X, Y, Z) = (Z - p_1 p_2 p_3 \cdots p_k, Y, Z)} \text{----- } (\mathbb{D})$$

Let's prove it as in 1-1.

Absurdity - Assuming that the above ordered pair (\mathbb{D}) is possible.

Let's replace P with

$$P = p_1 p_2 p_3 \cdots p_k$$

$$X = Z - P$$

$$Y = Y$$

$$Z = Z$$

Substitute this into 'Fermat equation'.

Remember that it comes out similar to 1-1

$$(Z - P)^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} P + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} P^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 P^{n-2} \\ + \binom{n}{n-1} Z P^{n-1} - P^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Y^n \\ = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} P - \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} P^2 + \dots + \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 P^{n-2} \\ - \binom{n}{n-1} Z P^{n-1} + P^n$$

$P \mid Y^n$ and $P \mid Y$ (\because Lemma 5.)

' $Y=Py$ '

$$P^n y^n + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} P^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 P^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z P^{n-1} \\ - P^n = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} P$$

$$P \times M = nZ^{n-1}$$

n is a single prime number.

But $P = p_1 p_2 p_3 \dots p_k$ is not.

Since $n \nmid Y$, $n \nmid P$, too.

Therefore Z contains P. $P \mid Z^n$ and $P \mid Z$.

It means Z contains all p_i , which is the prime factors of $P = p_1 p_2 p_3 \cdots p_k$. ($1 \leq i \leq k$)

Since p_i is a prime number, it is obvious that $p_i \geq 2$.

Let $Z = p_i z$ for some suitable natural number z .

And let $P = p_i q$, where $q = \frac{P}{p_i}$

It is already contradiction. Why?

$$X = Z - P = p_i z - p_i q = p_i (z - q)$$

$Y = Py$, it is a multiple of p_i

$$Z = p_i z$$

We can see that the ordered pair (X, Y, Z) has a common prime factor p_i .

It is contradiction because we assumed that X, Y, Z is coprime each other!

So we have checked that the cases

$$X=Z-p,$$

$$X=Z-p_1p_2p_3 \cdots p_k$$

is impossible.

How about this?

$$X = Z - p_1p_2^2p_3^2 \cdots p_k^2$$

It means the difference between Z and X is expressed by 1st square prime factor p_1 , and the others are prime with multi powers.

For example, $Z=463, X=13$

$$Z - X = 450 = 2 \times 3^2 \times 5^2$$

Is it possible?

The difference between Z and X is

$$Z - X = p_1p_2^2p_3^2 \cdots p_k^2$$

$$\text{Let } Q = \frac{Z-X}{p_1}.$$

Then $Z - X = p_1 \times Q$ for coprime p_1 and Q .

$$X=Z - p_1 Q \quad (\gcd(p_1, Q) = 1)$$

$$Y=Y$$

$$Z=Z$$

Substitute this into the 'Fermat equation'

$$\begin{aligned} & Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p_1 Q + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p_1^2 Q^2 - \dots \\ & - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p_1^{n-2} Q^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p_1^{n-1} Q^{n-1} - p_1^n Q^n + Y^n \\ & = Z^n \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & Y^n \\ & = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p_1 Q - \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p_1^2 Q^2 + \dots + \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p_1^{n-2} Q^{n-2} \\ & - \binom{n}{n-1} Z p_1^{n-1} Q^{n-1} + p_1^n Q^n \end{aligned}$$

$$Y^n = p_1 \times K$$

Y is a multiple of p_1 . So let $Y = p_1 y$. Substitute it into the equation above.

$$\begin{aligned} & p_1^n y^n + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p_1^2 Q^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 p_1^{n-2} Q^{n-2} \\ & + \binom{n}{n-2} Z p_1^{n-1} Q^{n-1} - p_1^n Q^n = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p_1 Q \end{aligned}$$

Divide both sides by p_1 . Then

$$p_1 \times K = n Z^{n-1} Q$$

$$p_1 \times K = nZ^{n-1}Q$$

p_1 is coprime to Q . Therefore $p_1 \mid Z^{n-1}$. ($\because \gcd(p_1, n) = 1$)

But $p_1 \mid Z^{n-1}$ is impossible. Because it means $p_1 \mid Z$.

In previous page,

$$X = Z - p_1Q = p_1z - p_1Q = p_1(z - Q)$$

$$Y = Y$$

$$Z = Z = p_1z$$

X and Z is not coprime. So it is contradiction.

Therefore,

$$Z - X = p_1 \times Q$$

(p_1 and Q are coprime)

all case of this form is impossible. For example,

$$Z - X = p_1 p_2 p_3^2 p_4^6$$

$$Z - X = p_1 p_2^7 p_3^{61}$$

$$Z - X = p_1 p_2^2 p_3^2 p_4^2 p_5^{1557} p_6^{564226}$$

⋮

These are all included in case above,

$$Z - X = p_1 \times Q$$

Now, let's check whether $X = Z - p^2$ is possible.

The logic used is pretty much the same as what we've been using so far in Chapter 1-1, 1-2

Next Chapter 1-3,

I'll prove that $X = Z - p^2$ is impossible, and additionally I will prove

$$X = Z - p^2 \times Q$$

is impossible. (p and Q is coprime)

Chapter 1-3

Let's assume that exists the following disjoint ordered pair
(X,Y,Z)

$$X=Z - p^2$$

$$Y=Y$$

$$Z=Z$$

$$(Z - p^2)^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Z^n - \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p^2 + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 (p^2)^{n-2} \\ + \binom{n}{n-1} Z (p^2)^{n-1} - p^{2n} + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$Y^n = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-1} Z (p^2)^{n-1} + p^{2n}$$

$$Y^n = p^2 \times K$$

We can know Y^n is a multiple of p^2

But... can we say Y is a multiple of p^2 ?

No. Counter example)

$$p=5 \text{ and } p^2 = 25, n=3. Y=5 \times 3$$

Y is not a multiple of 25, but $Y^3 = 5^3 \times 3^3$ is a multiple of 125.

So all we know for sure is that Y is a multiple of p.

Let $Y=py$. Then

$$X=Z - p^2$$

$$Y=py$$

$$Z=Z$$

$$p^n y^n + \binom{n}{2} Z^{n-2} p^4 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} Z^2 (p^2)^{n-2} \\ + \binom{n}{n-1} Z (p^2)^{n-1} - p^{2n} = \binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p^2$$

Divide both sides by p^2 .

$$p^{n-2} y^n + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} Z p^{2n-4} - p^{2n-2} = n Z^{n-1}$$

Since n is greater than or equal to 3,

The left-hand side is a multiple of p .

So

$$p \mid Z$$

It is impossible. Because $Z=pz$ means X and Z have a common divisor p . Look at the form of the ordered pair above.

Chapter 1-3)

$(Z - X)$ must be n-th power.

Therefore $(Z-Y) = p^2$ is impossible.

In a similar way, we can show that $(Z - X) = p^2 \times Q$ is also impossible. (Q is coprime to p^2).

How about this?

$$(Z - X) = p^3$$

If $n=3$, no contradiction is induced by the method of Lemma4.

But if $n=5,7,11,13\dots$

This still leads to a contradiction by Lemma4.

Do you see the rule?

In the Fermat equation with exponent n ,

$$(Z - X) = p^n$$

$(Z-X) = n$ -th power is possible and any other exponent causes a contradiction.

How about this?

$$(Z - X) = p^n \times q^{n-2}$$

Since it is not a n -th power, it causes contradiction by Lemma7.

(next page)

$$Y^n = (Z - X) \times \Phi_n(Z, X) \quad (\alpha)$$

If $(Z - X) = p^n \times q^{n-2}$,

Y must be a multiple of pq . Let $Y = pqy$

Then Y^n is a multiple of $p^n q^n$.

This causes contradiction. Since $X = Z - p^n q^{n-2}$, if we expand

$$(Z - p^n q^{n-2})^n + p^n q^n y^n = Z^n$$

Z^n on both sides are canceled and we get a term

$$\binom{n}{1} Z^{n-1} p^n q^{n-2}$$

All terms except this term is a multiple of $p^n q^n$. So by Lemma4, it is contradiction.

In general, if factorization of $(Z - X)$ is

$$(Z - X) = p_1^{r_1} \times p_2^{r_2} \times \dots \times p_m^{r_m}$$

By (α) , Y must have p_i to the

$$\left[\frac{r_i}{n} + 1 \right]$$

for all $1 \leq i \leq m$

$[]$ is the Gaussian symbol. If any r_i is not a multiple of n , the Fermat equation is contradiction by Lemma4.

Therefore $(Z - X)$ must be n -th power.

$$Z - X = R^n$$

$$Y^n = Z^n - X^n = (Z - X) \times \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

Y must be a multiple of R^n . If not, Y^n cannot be a multiple of $(Z - X)$.

$$Y = RA$$

Therefore the ordered pair (X, Y, Z) must be

$$(Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

R is coprime to A . Because if $\gcd(R, A) = g \geq 2$,

$$(Z - R^n)^n + R^n A^n = Z^n$$

Z^n on both sides are canceled and $R^n A^n$ is a multiple of g^{2n} .

all terms except $-\binom{n}{1}Z^{n-1}R^n$ is a multiple of g^{2n} .

So this is contradiction. Therefore $\gcd(R, A) = 1$

Since $Z - X = R^n$

Chapter 2.

Repeat same logic as Chapter 1

If $Z - X = R^n$ is impossible,

$$Z - Y = L^n$$

is also impossible. Because X and Y are interchangeable.

Same logic can be repeated as Chapter 1.

Note: The following form must be always satisfied:

$$X = Z - R^n \text{ and } Y = RA$$

$$X = LB \text{ and } Y = Z - L^n$$

$$\gcd(R, L) = 1$$

Because, if we choose $X = LB, Y = RA,$

$$(X, Y, Z) = (LB, RA, Z)$$

Since $\gcd(X, Y) = 1,$ L and R must also be coprime.

Chapter 3.

$$X + Y = G^n$$

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

Let's call it Fermat equation. We will talk about the case

$$n \nmid XYZ$$

For a prime number exponent n , ($n \geq 3$)

$$\begin{aligned} X^n + Y^n &= (X + Y)(X^{n-1} - X^{n-2}Y + X^{n-3}Y^2 - \dots + X^2Y^{n-3} - XY^{n-2} \\ &\quad + Y^{n-1}) \end{aligned}$$

Let

$$(X^{n-1} - X^{n-2}Y + \dots - XY^{n-2} + Y^{n-1}) = \phi(X, Y)$$

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n$$

$$(X + Y) \times \phi(X, Y) = Z^n$$

Therefore,

$$(X + Y) \mid Z^n$$

If $X + Y = P$ (P is a prime number)

Then Z must be a multiple of P , and Z^n is a multiple of P^n .

Substitute

$$X = (P - Y), Y = Y, Z = Pz$$

into the Fermat equation.

$$(P - Y)^n + Y^n = (PZ)^n$$

$$P^n - \binom{n}{1} P^{n-1} Y + \binom{n}{2} P^{n-2} Y^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} P^2 Y^{n-2} \\ + \binom{n}{n-1} P Y^{n-1} - Y^n + Y^n = P^n Z^n$$

$-Y^n + Y^n$ are canceled and divide both sides by P .

$$P^{n-1} - \binom{n}{1} P^{n-2} Y + \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} P Y^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1} Y^{n-1} \\ = P^{n-2} Z^n$$

Since $n \geq 3$, the right-hand side is a multiple of P .

And on the left-hand side, all terms except $\binom{n}{n-1} Y^{n-1}$ is a multiples of P .

($\because X, Y, Z$ are coprime each other, so P is coprime to X, Y)

It is contradiction. (by Lemma 2)

Therefore, $X + Y = P$ is impossible. (P is a prime number)

How about this?

$$X + Y = P^2$$

$$(X + Y) \mid Z^n$$

$$Z = Pz \quad (\because \text{Lemma 5})$$

$$X = P^2 - Y, Y = Y, Z = Pz$$

Let's use same logic.

$$(P^2 - Y)^n + Y^n = (Pz)^n$$

$$P^{2n} - \binom{n}{1} P^{2(n-1)}Y + \binom{n}{2} P^{2(n-2)}Y^2 - \dots - \binom{n}{n-2} P^4 Y^{n-2} \\ + \binom{n}{n-1} P^2 Y^{n-1} - Y^n + Y^n = P^n z^n$$

$-Y^n + Y^n$ are canceled and Divide both sides by P^2 .

Then the right-hand side is a multiple of P .

The left-hand side, on the other hand, all terms except $\binom{n}{n-1} Y^{n-1}$ are multiples of P .

It is contradiction by Lemma 4.

If we repeat this process, the only case where there is no contradiction is when

$$X + Y = P^n$$

How about the case

$$X + Y = P^n q$$

(q is another single prime number)

A similar logic process is repeated.

$$(X + Y) | Z^n$$

$$Z = Pqz$$

$$X = P^n q - Y, \quad Y = Y$$

$$(P^n q - Y)^n + Y^n = (Pqz)^n$$

$$P^{n^2} q^n - \binom{n}{1} P^{n(n-1)} q^{n-1} Y + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} P^n q Y^{n-1} - Y^n + Y^n = P^n q^n z^n$$

$-Y^n + Y^n$ are canceled and divide both sides by $P^n q$.

$$P^{n(n-1)}q^{n-1} - \binom{n}{1}P^{n(n-2)}q^{n-2} + \dots - \binom{n}{n-2}P^nqY^{n-2} + \binom{n}{n-1}Y^{n-1} = q^{n-1}z^n$$

There is no contradiction with respect to P .

But the right-hand side is a multiple of q .

On the left-hand side, all terms except $\binom{n}{n-1}Y^{n-1}$ is multiples of q .

So it is contradiction.

$$X + Y = P^nq$$

is impossible.

A very similar logic is repeated for

$$X + Y = P^nq^2$$

We can see that no contradiction occurs only when

$$X + Y = P^nq^n$$

The same logic is repeated for

$$X + Y = P^n q_1^n q_2^n$$

$X + Y$ must satisfy the form

$$X + Y = P^n q_1^n q_2^n \cdots q_k^n$$

In other words, if there is a natural number solution (X, Y, Z) in Fermat equation,

$(X + Y)$ must be a n -th power.

Let

$$X + Y = G^n$$

We've derived that

$$X = Z - R^n$$

$$Y = Z - L^n$$

Therefore,

$$(Z - R^n) + (Z - L^n) = G^n$$

Chapter 4.

Combine ①,②,③

$$Z - X = R^n, \quad \text{①}$$

$$Z - Y = L^n, \quad \text{②}$$

$$X + Y = G^n, \quad \text{③}$$

$$X + Y = (Z - R^n) + (Z - L^n) = G^n$$

$$2Z - R^n - L^n = G^n$$

$$2Z = G^n + R^n + L^n$$

$$\therefore Z = \frac{G^n + R^n + L^n}{2}$$

$$X = Z - R^n = \frac{G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}$$

$$Y = Z - L^n = \frac{G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}$$

As a result, (X, Y, Z) must satisfy the form

$$(X, Y, Z) = \left(\frac{G^n - R^n + L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n - L^n}{2}, \frac{G^n + R^n + L^n}{2} \right)$$

References

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